

Enrich your Energy Efficiency consultancy with evidence based INDUCE methodology as base for capacity building programs

INDUCE offers an open access platform with training material, online lessons, guidelines and tools to design tailor-made capacity building programs for increasing the energy efficiency of food & beverage enterprises.

With the capacity building programs, energy consultants provide advice on the implementation of energy efficiency measures related to **socio-cultural, organizational and technical aspects**.

A **Human-Centered Design approach** is at the basis of these capacity building programs which:

 Enables the design of **tailor-made training courses** that are adapted to the specific needs and opportunities within the enterprise

 Empowers all the relevant actors to develop energy efficient behaviour

 Creates an **energy efficiency culture** through training and motivation of the employees

 Results in the **following achievement** (based on the average of the 15 pilot companies in the project):

- Yearly energy savings: **1,296,882 kWh/y**
- Energy costs avoided: **63,501 €/y**
- GHG avoided: **300,879 kgCO2/year**

Human-Centered Design approach:

Stage I & II:

Inspiration & Ideation: Identifying challenges, expectation and needs, and generating ideas for capacity building program (multiple iterations)

- Collect information (data)
- Co-creation and introductory session with top management.
- Introductory interactive workshop with general employees.

Stage III:

Implementation: Carrying out trainings

- Top management trainings in motivating their employees and communicating energy efficiency issues.
- Middle management trainings on energy audits, energy management, energy.

Stage IV:

Review of the results and identify activities for further dissemination

- Top management co-creation sessions to evaluate the training.
- Final interactive workshop with general employees.

INDUCE Human-Centered Design Approach

All core-elements of the INDUCE capacity building programs are available in the [INDUCE open access platform](#) (after free registration).

Available information specific on the INDUCE capacity building programs

 Documents – All documents that allow for implementation of the INDUCE capacity building programs. It includes technical (understand and control energy use), organizational (management commitment, resources and planning) and cultural aspects (people’s motivations and behaviour). The documents are available in English, Dutch, French, German and Spanish.

 Resources - All the resources that can be used to carry out each training unit and to make up the module or course

 Units - All training units designed and used with the pilot companies in the INDUCE project

Available information on generic energy efficiency programs:

 Projects – An overview on running and already finished projects

 Energy Efficiency Tools – More than 160 existing energy efficiency tools and capacity building programs. Filtering is possible by (i) sector of the enterprise, (ii) target groups within the enterprise, (iii) learning types (conceptual, procedural), (iv) technical aspects, (v) methods & activities, (vi) resource types (e.g. case study, tests, video) and (vii) per language.

 Energy Efficiency Measures – A repository of energy efficiency measures to find the best solution for each specific situation. It will be possible to filter by (i) category (e.g. management, process-specific), (ii) area (e.g. buildings, processes, food processing...), (iii) sub-areas (e.g. building envelope, building heating), (iv) implementation effort and (v) saving potential.

Next to the platform, additional information on the INDUCE project, the Human-Centred Design approach and the impact of the INDUCE capacity building program can be found in the deliverables on the [INDUCE website](#).

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